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15-16 March, 2022

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UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES
Raichur - 584 104, Karnataka, India

Ph: 08532-220152 Toll Free No. 1800 4250 470

e-mail: nahepig@uasraichur.edu.in

www.uasraichur.edu.in

Opportunities for Digital Agricultural Education in National Education Policy-2020

Nasratullah* Manjula. N.** S.S.Dolli*** and Krishna Gudadur****

Ph.D Scholar* Professor** Professor*** and Ph.D Scholar****

University of Agricultural Sciences Dharwad
Department of Agricultural Extension Education
Email: nasratkakar3@gmail.com

During COVID-19 pandemic most Indian states have transferred their classrooms to the cloud, frequently cooperating with others, and classrooms resemble the screen of a desktop or laptop computer. Zoom, Google Meet, YouTube, Skype, and WebEx are a few examples. Become the new face of teaching classrooms in which teachers interact with their learners online and educate virtually. In one sense, this shifting paradigm of teaching opens new horizons for learning; nevertheless, it also causes a problem in another sense, where agricultural education, which is mostly centred on practical and field-based instruction, suffers a lot. Some initiatives of government of India for agricultural digital education are DIKSHA, SWAYAM online courses, UG/PG MOOCs, e-PG Pathashala, e-Content courseware in UG subjects, SWAYAMPRAKASHA, CEC-UGC YouTube channel, National Digital Library, Shodhganga, e-Shodh Sindhu and Vidwan, etc. For school students as well as UG and PG level education, it is extremely difficult to bring all learners under the same platform in equal manner where several challenges of basic infrastructure development is in its midstream and technology reach is awaited. The study conducted in UAS, Dharwad regarding utilization of ICT tools by faculty and students in agricultural education. Study revealed that (38%) faculty were using ICT tools at low extent followed by (32%) and (30%) medium extent and high extent respectively. In case of students, medium level utilization of ICT tools was more (42.67%) followed by low (29.33%) and high level (28%) respectively. There is ample scope for adopting ICT in teaching and learning on farm Universities under NEP-2020.

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Nasratullah Kakar, Manjula. N., S.S.Doll and Krishna Gudadur

University of Agricultural Sciences, Dharwad

Introduction

Information Communication Technology (ICT) consists of a distinct set of technological tools and resources to create, disseminate, store and manage data and information. Conventional ICT tools like T.V., radio and telephone have already established their credibility and effectiveness in promoting the developmental schemes in rural and backward areas. The modern ICT tools are computers, internet and wireless communication technology in addition of powerful software's which can process and integrate sound, text and video into electronic media. ICT has the ability to prepare learners for a rapidly changing world scenario. They may use ICT as a tool to identify, analyze, exchange and present information as per their need. Information and communication technology (ICT) in education is the method of education that use information and communication technology to support, improve, and optimize the delivery of information. Information and communication technology can lead to improved student learning and superior teaching methods. The findings regarding utilization of ICT tools by the teachers may help the administrators and policy makers for formulating effective implementation strategy and policies regarding.

Objective

To study the utilization pattern of ICT tools in agricultural education by faculty and students.

Material and Methods

The present study was conducted during November 2021 to know the utilization pattern of ICT tools in agricultural education by faculty and students.

The samples for the study were 100 faculty members and 150 students from all colleges of University of Agricultural Sciences, Dharwad. Thus the total samples for the study were 250 faculty members and students.

Information was collected through personal interview using the structured schedule developed for the study.

Results and Discussion

The data present in Table-1 that most extent utilization ICT tool by teachers was Internet/ web services ranked at first with mean score of (3.98) followed by MS Word (3.97) ranked II, Email (3.80) ranked III, MS Excel (3.39) ranked IV, MS PowerPoint (3.37) ranked V, , YouTube (3.16) ranked VI, Wikipedia (2.99) ranked VII, Agricultural web portals (2.63) ranked VIII respectively. With respect to students the most extent utilization ICT tools was also Internet/ web services ranked at first with mean score of 3.92 followed by YouTube (3.63) ranked II, Email (3.59) ranked III, MS Word (3.23) ranked IV, Wikipedia (3.14) ranked V, MS Excel (2.78) ranked VI, MS PowerPoint (2.71) ranked VII, MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) (2.39) ranked VIII respectively.

The table-2 shows that (38%) teachers was using ICT tools at medium extent followed by (32%) and (30%) low extent and high extent respectively. In case of students, medium level utilization of ICT tools was more (42.67%) followed by low (29.33%) and high level (28%) respectively.

Table-1: Distribution of the respondents according to extent of utilization ICT tools by teachers and students

Sl. No.	ICT Tools	Teachers n=100			Students n=150		
		Total Score	Mean Score	Ranked Order	Total Score	Mean Score	Ranked Order
1	Internet/ web services	398	3.98	I	588	3.92	I
2	MS Word	393	3.97	II	469	3.23	IV
3	MS Excel	332	3.39	IV	384	2.78	VI
4	MS PowerPoint	330	3.37	V	395	2.71	VII
5	Analytic package SPSS	128	1.78	XIII	154	2.30	XII
6	m-Stat	79	1.49	XV	84	2.21	XIII
7	Geographical Information System (GIS)	73	1.62	XIV	136	2.39	IX
8	Kiosks	53	1.83	XII	75	2.14	XIV
9	Email	380	3.80	III	514	3.59	III
10	MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses)	99	1.94	XI	129	2.39	VIII
11	Wikipedia	227	2.99	VII	436	3.14	V
12	YouTube	291	3.16	VI	526	3.63	II
13	Online thesis repositories	166	2.02	X	174	2.32	XI
14	CeRA	121	2.05	IX	91	2.07	XV
15	Agricultural web portals	237	2.63	VIII	248	2.38	X

Level of utilization ICT tools by teachers and students

Teachers			Students		
Category	F	%	Category	F	%
Low <30	32	32.00	Low <26	44	29.33
Medium 30-36	38	38.00	Medium 26-33	64	42.67
High >36	30	30.00	High >33	42	28.00
Mean = 33.06	SD = 7.99		Mean = 29.35	SD = 8.77	

Conclusion

Most extent utilization ICT tool by teachers was Internet/ web services ranked at first with mean score of 3.98 followed by MS Word (3.97) ranked II and Email (3.80) ranked III. In case of students Most extent utilization ICT tool was also Internet/ web services ranked at first with mean score of 3.92 followed by YouTube (3.63) ranked II and Email (3.59) ranked III respectively. Maximum number of teachers (38%) and maximum (42.67%) of students both categories were observed using ICT tools at medium extent level respectively.